

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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A systematic literature review on public health and healthcare resources for pandemic preparedness planning

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Abstract

Background Generating insights into resource demands during outbreaks is an important aspect of pandemic preparedness. The EU PANDEM-2 project used resource modelling to explore the demand profile for key resources during pandemic scenarios. This review aimed to identify public health and healthcare resources needed to respond to pandemic threats and the ranges of parameter values on the use of these resources for pandemic influenza (including the novel influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 pandemic) and the COVID-19 pandemic, to support modelling activities.

Methods We conducted a systematic literature review and searched Embase and Medline databases (1995 – June 2023) for articles that included a model, scenario, or simulation of pandemic resources and/or describe resource parameters, for example personal protective equipment (PPE) usage, length of stay (LoS) in intensive care unit (ICU), or vaccine efficacy. Papers with data on resource parameters from all countries were included.

Results We identified 2754 articles of which 147 were included in the final review. Forty-six different resource parameters with values related to non-ICU beds ($n=43$ articles), ICU beds ($n=57$), mechanical ventilation ($n=39$), healthcare workers ($n=12$), pharmaceuticals ($n=21$), PPE ($n=8$), vaccines ($n=26$), and testing and tracing ($n=19$). Differences between resource types related to pandemic influenza and COVID-19 were observed, for example on mechanical ventilation (mostly for COVID-19) and testing & tracing (all for COVID-19).

Conclusion This review provides an overview of public health and healthcare resources with associated parameters in the context of pandemic influenza and the COVID-19 pandemic. Providing insight into the ranges of plausible parameter values on the use of public health and healthcare resources improves the accuracy of results of modelling different scenarios, and thus decision-making by policy makers and hospital planners. This review also highlights a scarcity of published data on important public health resources.

Keywords Public health, Systematic review, COVID-19, Bed occupancy, Health Workforce

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Introduction

In the 21st century, two pandemics caused by respiratory viruses of zoonotic origin have been declared by the World Health Organization (WHO): the novel influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 pandemic and the COVID-19 pandemic. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic was unprecedented, as it involved all public health and healthcare domains and revealed important weaknesses of the health system. At various stages of the COVID-19 pandemic, health systems were unable to cope with the demand, for example on testing and tracing [1], hospital capacity [2, 3], stocks of personal protective equipment (PPE) [4] and morgue capacity [5].

Mathematical modelling is a key element for infectious diseases control, and its use has become more widespread in recent decades due to the increased availability of electronic data and computing power [6]. During the COVID-19 pandemic, models for epidemiological analysis and forecasting have been used by public health institutes and governments to inform policy, and also by universities and members of the public using publicly available epidemiological data. However, these epidemiological models generally did not provide direct insights in public health and healthcare resource demands [7]. Models that link projections of epidemiological outcomes with public health and healthcare resource capacities can be applied during multiple stages of the preparedness cycle [8]: to inform scenario development for governance, capacity building and maintenance, and risk assessment during the pre-event or cold phase, and for short-term forecasting to support risk and crisis management during the event or hot phase of an outbreak [9, 10]. Resource demands differ greatly between, and also within prolonged outbreaks and pandemics due to different epidemiological progression, availability (or lack thereof) and effectiveness of treatments or vaccines and different application of non-pharmaceutical interventions. This makes data on the availability and use of resources (pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical) extremely valuable. Addressing the resource modelling gap was one of the aims of PANDEM-2, an EU Horizon2020 project [11], of which this review was a part. PANDEM-2 delivered a dashboard with tools for pandemic preparedness and response, including a robust mathematical model that can inform policy makers on resource demands and utilisation, which was piloted during a functional exercise [12].

Modelling relies on robust, preferably real-world data to deliver accurate outcomes. Epidemiological data are widely available and have also been systematically collected for modelling purposes [13]. This is, however, not the case for data on public health and healthcare resources utilization, which are usually not systematically collected in a standardized and centralized manner,

nor are they part of routine infectious disease surveillance systems. This review sought to answer the question which public health and healthcare resource data from recent pandemics is available in scientific literature. In the context of this review, we define public health and healthcare resources as those directly relevant to the control or mitigation of a pandemic from a public health and healthcare perspective, as they are most relevant input data for modelling for pandemic preparedness or forecasting during pandemics. Non-medical resource costs, costs of non-pharmaceutical interventions and indirect costs (such as productivity loss) are of course extremely important for policy decisions, but they are beyond the scope of this work. The aim of this review therefore was to identify what resource data is available from scientific research on recent pandemics (the novel influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 and COVID-19 pandemics), and provide a comprehensive overview of resource data useful to mathematical modellers.

Methods

Scope

We provide an overview of public health and healthcare resources most likely to be needed in pandemics of respiratory pathogens, comparable to the novel influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 pandemic and the COVID-19 pandemic. Historic pandemics of a similar nature are not included as the advances in healthcare systems and medical countermeasures, including vaccines and technology, mean that their data may no longer be applicable to pandemic management in the 21st century.

Methodology

The systematic literature review was conducted according to guidelines presented in the PRISMA statement (Supplementary material 1) [14] and used the PCC (population, concept, context) framework to develop our research question and inform the search strategy, as it is more suitable for explorative review than the PICO (population, intervention, comparators, outcomes) framework commonly used for systematic literature reviews and meta-analysis [15]. Embase and Medline databases were searched through Embase.com using a search strategy developed with assistance from a scientific information specialist (Supplementary material 2). The search was first performed on the 21st of May 2021 and updated on the 25th of March 2022 and again on the 3rd of June 2023. Endnote 20 software [16] was used to support the review process.

Study selection

We included articles that (i) contain a model, scenario or simulation related to pandemic resources citing resource parameter data, or (ii) observational studies describing

resource parameters and associated values or rates. No specific population was targeted due to the diverse nature of studies we expected to include resource data from. We included articles published in the context of pandemics with a respiratory pathogen (pandemic influenza, novel influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 or COVID-19). We excluded articles written in a language other than English or Dutch (the native language of the researchers), articles on seasonal influenza, articles with non-human data, articles on historic pandemics of respiratory pathogens (such as the 1918–1920 flu pandemic) and articles published before 1995. The reference lists of review articles identified by our search strategy were screened for relevant original research papers. Commentaries, conference abstracts or editorials were excluded.

Articles were assessed by two researchers independently by screening the title and abstract, and subsequently by screening full texts of articles included after the first step. Disagreements about the inclusion of an article were resolved via discussion. If both researchers were still unsure about inclusion or rejection, a third researcher was consulted.

Data extraction

The following data were extracted from included articles: first author, year published, country and World Bank classification [17], study period, study design, study setting and disease type. In relation to resource data, we extracted the resource type and specific parameter, and the associated value.

Study quality

The aim of this review is to identify and extract resource parameter data from scientific publications for the purposes of mathematical modelling, and not to perform a meta-analysis of found resource parameters. Therefore, the 147 studies selected were not assessed for risk of bias within the individual studies or across studies, and no quality assessment was performed prior to data extraction.

Results

Search results

The initial search yielded 1166 articles and the two repeated searches added a further 788 and 758 articles to a total of 2712. After removing duplicates (8, 211, and 76 for the first, second and third searches respectively), the combined search yielded 2417 articles. Additionally, 40 articles were identified from reference lists and previous work done in the AsiaFluCap project [18]. In total, 2457 articles were screened for inclusion based on title and abstract (Fig. 1). 2087 articles were excluded, leaving 370 articles for full text analysis. Following full text analysis, 225 articles were excluded because they either did not

contain a description of pandemic resources ($n=112$), had a description of resources but did not report resource values ($n=94$), described pandemics occurring before 1995 ($n=9$) or reported resource data in settings unrelated to a pandemic ($n=10$). Following our screening process, 145 articles were finally included in this systematic review.

Study characteristics

We included 45 (31%) studies related to pandemic influenza, including novel influenza A(H1N1)pdm09, and 102 (69%) related to the COVID-19 pandemic (Table 1). Studies were conducted in 53 different countries, with the majority conducted in Europe (38%), North America (32%) and

Asia (20.7%). Several studies ($n=11$, 7.5%) were conducted in multiple countries. Most studies were conducted in high-income countries ($n=119$; 82.3%), followed by upper-middle income ($n=15$; 10.2%) and lower-middle income ($n=11$; 7.5%). Most included studies were model building studies ($n=70$; 47.6%), followed by observational studies ($n=50$; 34%), evaluations ($n=19$; 12.9%), clinical trials ($n=5$; 3.4%), surveys ($n=2$; 1.4%) and cost-benefit analyses ($n=1$; 0.7%). The majority of studies relating to pandemic influenza were model building studies, while for COVID-19 and the majority were observational studies, followed by model building studies. Research focus was similar for pandemic influenza and COVID-19, with the majority being hospital related. Studies relating to COVID-19 had slightly more diverse foci than those on pandemic influenza (9 vs. 5 different foci). The full list of included studies and characteristics is given in Supplementary Table 1.

Pandemic resources identified from literature

We identified 15 different resources with a total of 46 different resource parameters related to pandemic influenza and COVID-19 pandemic (Table 2). Resources were identified for both pandemic influenza and COVID-19, or either only for pandemic influenza or only for COVID-19.

Healthcare resources

Non intensive care unit beds

Use of general clinical departments (i.e. non-intensive care unit; non-ICU beds or ward beds) was reported in 43 publications: 14 for pandemic influenza and 29 for COVID-19 (Table 3). Usage was defined by the parameters admission rate and length of stay (LoS). For pandemic influenza, the non-ICU admission rate ranged between 0.4 and 11% for symptomatic cases [19–24], and 3% admission rate for patients who consulted a general practitioner (GP) [25], with an average LoS of 5–11 days [26–32]. For COVID-19, reported non-ICU admission

Fig. 1 PRISMA flowchart of studies included in this review

rates were between 1 and 37.6% for all symptomatic cases [33–39], 8.4% of all laboratory confirmed covid cases [40], 466.7 per 100,000 adults [41], 73.1% of confirmed COVID-19 cases in the emergency department [42] or 17.4% of cases from outbreaks in long-term care facilities

[43]. One study reported on admission rates for non-vaccinated (886 per 100,000), vaccinated (92 per 100,000) and boosted (43 per 100,000) individuals aged ≥ 12 years [44]. One study reported on admission rates per COVID-19 wave: pre-wave 1 (March – June 2020): 22.3%, wave

Table 1 Summary of study characteristics for the articles included in this review

	Total (n = 147)	Pandemic influenza ^a (n = 45)	COVID-19 (n = 102)
Region of study^b (n, %)			
Africa	5 (3.3%)	0 (0%)	5 (4.9%)
Asia	31 (20.7%)	11 (23.4%)	20 (19.4%)
Europe	57 (38%)	13 (27.7%)	44 (42.7%)
North America	48 (32%)	18 (38.3%)	30 (29.1%)
Oceania	5 (3.3%)	5 (10.6%)	0 (0%)
South America	4 (2.7%)	0 (0%)	4 (3.9%)
World Bank classification^c [17] (n, %)			
High income	119 (82.3%)	42 (91.3%)	77 (78.2%)
Upper middle income	15 (10.2%)	3 (6.5%)	12 (11.9%)
Lower middle income	11 (7.5%)	1 (2.2%)	10 (9.9%)
Study approach (n, %)			
Clinical trial	3 (3.4%)	1 (2.2%)	2 (3.9%)
Cost-benefit analysis	1 (0.7%)	1 (2.2%)	0 (0%)
Evaluation	19 (12.9%)	6 (13.3%)	13 (12.7%)
Model building	70 (47.6%)	34 (75.6%)	36 (35.3%)
Observational	50 (34%)	2 (4.4%)	48 (47.1%)
Survey	2 (1.4%)	1 (2.2%)	1 (1%)
Research focus^d(n, %)			
Contact tracing	3 (2%)	0 (0%)	3 (2.9%)
First responder ^e	3 (2%)	0 (0%)	3 (2.9%)
General practice	1 (0.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (1%)
Hospital	102 (70.3%)	33 (73.3%)	69 (68.9%)
Long-term care facilities	1 (0.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (1%)
Emergency preparedness	8 (5.4%)	4 (8.9%)	4 (3.9%)
Public health	8 (5.4%)	3 (6.7%)	5 (4.9%)
School	1 (0.7%)	1 (2.2%)	0 (0%)
Testing strategies	6 (4.1%)	0 (0%)	6 (5.8%)
Vaccination	13 (8.8%)	4 (8.9%)	9 (8.7%)

^aIncluding novel influenza A(H1N1)pdm09

^bThree studies included countries from multiple regions: 2x North America & Europe, 1x North America, Europe & Asia. One study includes global data and is not included in this count

^cOne study includes global data and is not included in this count. One study includes data from both upper middle income and lower middle income countries

^dOne study includes data on both contact tracing and testing strategies

^eIncludes paramedics and fire fighters responding to emergencies

1 (June – August 2020): 16.8%, post-wave 1 (August – November 2020): 22.2%, wave 2 (November 2020 – February 2021): 19.6% of all covid cases [45]. The average reported non-ICU LoS for COVID-19 patients varied between 2 and 31.8 days [20, 34–37, 39, 45–57]. One study specifically reported on pre- and post-ICU LoS on general wards: 2.7 and 13.6 days respectively [58]. One study reported a non-ICU LoS of 15.6 days during the first wave and a LoS of 11.6 days during the second wave [59]. One study reported on a non-ICU LoS of 9.2 days pre-Delta, 9.7 days during Delta and 7.1 days during Omicron; and non-ICU LoS of 10.6 days for vaccinated patients during Delta and 6.8 days LoS for vaccinated patients during Omicron, and 9.4 days for non-vaccinated patients during Delta and 7.8 days for non-vaccinated patients during Omicron [60].

Intensive care unit beds

Data on ICU bed use was reported in 57 studies (16 for pandemic influenza, 41 for COVID-19) (Table 3). Similar to the data on non-ICU beds, admission rate and LoS were identified as resource parameters. Additionally for COVID-19, surge capacity was also identified as an ICU bed parameter. For pandemic influenza, admission rates were all reported as a percentage of all hospitalized patients (12.8–36%) [21, 23, 24, 26, 29, 30, 61–64]. The average LoS on the ICU was 5.8–12 days [25, 26, 28–30, 46, 63, 65–67]. For COVID-19, ICU admission rates were either reported as percentage of all COVID-19 cases (4.6–8.7%) [35, 36, 68, 69], percentage of all COVID-19 hospitalizations (10.6–66%) [20, 33, 34, 37, 39, 44, 46, 47, 57, 70–76], percentage of COVID-19 cases presented at emergency department (ED) (13.4%) [42], as percentage of all laboratory confirmed cases (1.4%) [40] or as 136.6

Table 2 Overview of resources and associated parameters identified in this systematic review. ICU: Intensive Care Unit; ECMO: Extra Corporeal membrane oxygenation; HFNO: high Flow Nasal Oxygen; CPAP: continuous positive Airway pressure; PPE: personal protective equipment

Healthcare resources		Public health resources	
Non-ICU beds	Antivirals	Vaccines	Contact tracing
- Admission rate	- Dosage	- Dose frequency	- Adherence
- Length of stay	- Efficacy	- Vaccine administration speed	- Success rate
- Readmission rate	- Stockpiling	- Vaccination rate	- Speed
ICU Beds	- Use rate	- Manufacturing capacity	- Testing
- Admission rate	Other pharmaceuticals	- Efficacy	- Laboratory processing time
- Length of stay	- Dosage	- Effectiveness against transmission	- Time to test result
- Surge capacity	- Use rate	- Breakthrough transmission	Testing capacity
Readmission rate	PPE		- Test sensitivity
- Mechanical ventilation	- Use rate		- Test specificity
- Use rate	- Stockpiling		
- Duration	- Surge demand		
- ECMO use	Ambulances		
- HFNO use	- Arrival time		
- CPAP use	General practitioners		
Healthcare workers	- Consultation rate		
- Absenteeism	Palliative care		
- HCW to bed/patient ratio	- Care kits		
Antibiotics	- Use rate		
- Dosage	- Duration		
	Care seeking		
	- Outpatient care		
	- Inpatient care		

per 100,000 adults [41]. One study reported admission rates stratified by vaccination status (230.6 per 100,000 for non-vaccinated individuals, 30.8 per 100,000 for vaccinated individuals and 5.5 per 100,000 for boosted individuals) [77]. One study on ICU admission rates as 28.7% of hospitalized patients pre-Delta, 21.4% during Delta and 15.4% during Omicron, and ICU admission rates of vaccinated hospitalized patients as 22.8% during Delta and 14.2% during Omicron, and for non-vaccinated hospitalized patients 19.3% during Delta and 14.7% during Omicron [60]. Average LoS was reported as 3–26.9 days [20, 34–37, 39, 49, 51–53, 55–59, 69, 70, 75, 78–81]. One study reported on ICU LoS of 9.8 days pre-Delta, 9.4 days during Delta and 6.3 days during Omicron; and ICU LoS of 8 days for vaccinated patients during Delta and 4.8 days LoS for vaccinated patients during Omicron, and 11.6 days for non-vaccinated patients during Delta and 5.9 days for non-vaccinated patients during Omicron [60]. Surge capacity was reported as the possible percentage of normal non-pandemic ICU beds (115–1111%) [74, 82–86].

Mechanical ventilation

Mechanical ventilation was reported in 39 studies, ten relating to pandemic influenza and 29 for COVID-19 (Table 3). For pandemic influenza, mechanical ventilation was mainly reported as the percentage of patients requiring mechanical ventilation in ICU (50–93.2%) [21, 23, 26, 66] or in all hospitalized patients (7.5–30%) [61, 87–89]. The type of mechanical ventilation was not specified.

One study reported on the duration of mechanical ventilation for ICU patients with pandemic influenza (60% of patients require 1 week, 40% require two weeks) [21]. For COVID-19, we identified rates of need for mechanical ventilation, type unspecified (26 studies), extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO, six studies, 0.2–1.5% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations [55, 60, 75] and 3–31% of ICU patients [54, 80, 90]), high-flow nasal oxygen (HFNO, four studies, 0.5–3.3% of COVID-19 hospitalizations [59, 71] and 5–17.4% of ICU patients [67, 90]) and continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP, two studies, 0.2% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations [59] and 48.6% of ICU patients [67]). The reported rates of use for unspecified mechanical ventilation were 6.1% for all COVID-19 cases [35], 7–39.8% of COVID-19 hospitalizations [48, 53, 56, 59, 68, 71, 72, 75, 76, 91, 92] and 26.4–88% for ICU patients [20, 24, 33, 37, 49, 54, 55, 69, 74, 93–95]. One study reported on mechanical ventilation use of 11.8% for all COVID-19 hospitalizations pre-Delta, 13.4% during Delta and 7.6% during Omicron, and mechanical ventilation use of 12.4% for all vaccinated COVID-19 hospitalizations during Delta and 6.4% during Omicron, and 13.5% for all non-vaccinated COVID-19 hospitalizations during Delta and 7.2% during Omicron [60]. Eight studies also reported on the duration of mechanical ventilation for COVID-19 patients (median 8–18 days) [20, 35, 49, 54–56, 78, 90].

Table 3 Description of extracted resource parameters for non-intensive care unit (ICU) beds, ICU beds, mechanical ventilation, healthcare workers and vaccines. Data stratified by different COVID-19 waves or vaccination status are not included in this table. GP: general practitioner, ED: emergency department, ECMO: extra corporeal membrane oxygenation, HFNO: high flow nasal oxygen, CPAP: continuous positive airway pressure, VET: vaccine effectiveness against transmission

	Pandemic influenza ^a	COVID-19
Non-ICU beds		
Number of studies	14	29
Admission rate		
(% of symptomatic cases)	0.4–11%	-
(% of all cases)	-	1–37.6%
(% of GP consultations)	3% of patients who consulted a GP	-
(% of confirmed cases visiting ED)	-	73.1%
(% of laboratory confirmed cases)	-	8.4%
(per 100000 adults)	-	466.7
Length of stay (days)	5–11	2–31.8
ICU beds		
Number of studies	16	41
Admission rate		
(% of hospital admissions)	12.8–36%	10.6–66%
(% of all cases)	-	4.6–8.7%
(% of COVID-19 cases visiting ED)	-	13.4%
(% of all laboratory confirmed cases)	-	1.4%
(per 100000 adults)	-	136.6
Length of stay (days)	5.8–12	3–26.9
Surge capacity (%)	-	115–1111%
Mechanical ventilation		
Number of studies	10	29
Need for mechanical ventilation		
(% of hospitalized patients)	7.5–30%	7–39.8%
(% of ICU patients)	50–93.2%	26.4–88%
(% of all COVID-19 confirmed cases)	-	6.1%
Duration (days)	7–14	8–18
ECMO use		
(% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations)	-	0.2–1.5%
(% of ICU patients)	-	3–31%
HFNO use		
(% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations)	-	0.5–3.3%
(% of ICU patients)	-	5–17.4%
CPAP use		
(% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations)	-	0.2%
(% of ICU patients)	-	48.6%
Healthcare workers		
Number of studies	5	7
Absenteeism (prevalence %)	10–56.6%	3.3–17%
Capacity	5 patients per regular ward nurse 10 patients per regular ward physician	0.4–1.6 patients per ICU nurse 7 patients per intensivist
Vaccines		
Number of studies	15	11
Dose frequency	1–2 per patient	-
Efficacy (%)	35–52% for susceptibility	Symptomatic COVID-19: 35% (1 dose BNT162b2), 59% (2 doses) Asymptomatic COVID-19: 35% (1 dose BNT126b2), 49% (2 doses)
	80% for illness given infection	94.6–95 (BNT162b2) 93.6 (Moderna) 60 (AstraZeneca) 65.8–67 (Janssen, single dose)

Table 3 (continued)

	Pandemic influenza ^a	COVID-19
Efficacy, other	Vaccinated elderly patients: 1.31 chest X-rays Unvaccinated elderly patients: 2.61 chest X-rays Antibiotics duration vaccinated patients: 2.32 days (oral), 2.55 days (IV) Antibiotics duration unvaccinated patients: 3.98 days (oral), 7.52 days (IV)	VET of BNT162b2: 96% (Alpha), 87% (Delta), 31% (Omicron). VET of BNT162b2 booster: 87% (Delta), 68% (Omicron)
Administering speed	17.5–30 vaccines per nurse per hour	1284–50,000 per day 0.27–8.27 doses per 100 people per day
Manufacturing capacity	22 million doses per week (globally)	-

^aIncluding novel influenza A(H1N1)pdm09

Healthcare workers

Parameters concerning healthcare workers (HCW) were identified in five studies for pandemic influenza and seven studies for COVID-19 (Table 3). For general HCW, absenteeism during the H1N1 influenza pandemic was reported as between 10 and 30% [87, 89, 96]. For emergency department staff, one study reported 36% becoming ill with influenza-like illness, and of these, 56.6% having at least one day of absence and a mean of 3.73 days of absence [97]. For COVID-19, absenteeism due to illness was reported as 3.3–14.6% for HCWs [93], 12.1% for ICU nurses [98] and 17% for general practice front-line workers [99]. Absenteeism due to burnout (6.9%) was also reported for HCWs during the COVID-19 pandemic [3]. Healthcare worker capacity was reported as the number of patients that can be attended per nurse or physician per shift, or number of nurses per bed. For pandemic influenza, this was reported as 10 patients for one physician and five patients for one nurse during daytime shifts (40 per physician and 20 per nurse during night time shifts) [100]. For COVID-19, this was reported for intensive care unit (ICU) capacity as 1–1.6 patients per nurse per shift [101, 102] or 2.26:1 nurse to bed ratio [74], seven patients per intensivist and 4 patients per respiratory therapist [101].

Antivirals, antibiotics and other pharmaceuticals

Twenty-one studies reporting on antivirals, antibiotics or other pharmaceuticals as a resource for treatment were identified, 10 regarding pandemic influenza and 11 regarding COVID-19 (Supplementary Table 2). For pandemic influenza we found oseltamivir prophylaxis or treatment (one dose of 75 mg per day for prophylaxis, two doses per day for 5–7 days for treatment) [65, 100, 103–105] and efficacy (60–89%) [106–108], zanamivir treatment (20 mg per day for 5 days) [103] and efficacy (61–62%) [106, 107], amantadine treatment (200 mg daily) [103] and efficacy (61%) [106] and rimantadine efficacy (72%) [106]. Two studies also reported on the required or estimated stockpile of antivirals

(recommending a stockpile sufficient for either 4–6% [19] or 25% [109] of the population). One study also reported on the use of antibiotics (amoxicillin and co-trimoxazole) in patients with pandemic influenza [100].

For COVID-19, studies reported remdesivir treatment (200 mg on day 1, followed by 100 mg per day up to day 10) [110, 111], rate of use (4.5% of ICU patients [67] or 2.8% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations [112]) and effect (30% relative reduction in progression to ICU [39]). One study reported on general use of antivirals during the first wave (6.7% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations) and the second wave (1.5%) [59]. Dexamethasone was also reported as a treatment for COVID-19, with treatment (1 dose of 6 mg per day up to 10 days) [110, 113] and rate of use (2.2% of COVID-19 patients in March–June 2020 [71], 34% of COVID-19 hospitalizations in January 2022 [114]). Use of steroids as therapeutics was reported in two publications as 9.5% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations during the first wave and 28% during the second [59] and 11.1% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations during the second wave [112]. Two studies on the effect of hydroxychloroquine were included. One study reported a dosage of 600 mg per day and no reduction in ICU admissions or deaths in hospitalized COVID-19 pneumonia patients receiving oxygen, and no effect on survival in hospitalized COVID-19 patients without acute respiratory distress syndrome [115]. The other study reported a range of dosages (200 mg, 400 mg and 600 mg per dose, either once or twice daily) and no significant differences in in-hospital mortality between patients receiving hydroxychloroquine treatment and control group [116].

Personal protective equipment

Eight studies reported on the usage of personal protective equipment (PPE), with six regarding pandemic influenza and two regarding COVID-19 (Supplementary Table 2). For pandemic influenza, three studies reported on the composition of PPE kits in hospitals [89, 117, 118] and two on the rate of use: 20–25 PPE kits per patient in the first six hours of treatment [119], or 91 surgical

masks and 40 N95 masks per hospitalized patient [100]. One study reported on stockpiling PPE kits for pandemic influenza for a hospital [117]. For COVID-19, we found a reported daily use of 195 PPE kits per occupied hospital bed during March & April 2020 [120], and an increased demand for surgical masks (355%), surgical gowns (1105%), plastic aprons (443%) and hand sanitizer (136%), also during the first wave of COVID-19 [121].

Other healthcare resources

Several publications reporting on other aspects of care as pandemic related resources were identified (Supplementary Table 2). Three studies reported on delayed arrival times (5–15 min) [122–124] for ambulances during the COVID-19 pandemic. Two studies reported on GP consultations related to pandemic influenza: 12% of the population consulted the GP [25], one patient visited the GP an average of 2.1 times [63] and 60.5% of hospitalized patients have visited the GP before or after hospitalization for pandemic influenza [63]. One study reported on care seeking behaviour during the COVID-19 pandemic: 83% of those tested who positive sought outpatient care during the 1st wave, 81% (2nd wave), 69% (3rd wave) and 59% (4th wave); for inpatient care this amounted to 4.9% of those who tested positive during the 1st wave, 3.6% (2nd wave), 1.4% (3rd wave) and 0.5% (4th wave) [125]. One study reported that COVID-19-related readmissions within 30 days occurred for 5.3% of all COVID-19 hospitalizations, and readmission to ICU for 1.3% of COVID-19 hospitalizations; for 4.1% of COVID-19 outpatients COVID-19-related hospitalization occurred within 30 days, for 0.7% this was COVID-19-related ICU admission [75]. For palliative care during the COVID-19 pandemic, one study reported the need for palliative care for 22.3% of hospitalized patients, with an average duration of 2 days [126]. One study made recommendations on the need for stockpiling of, and contents of palliative care kits [127].

Public health resources

Vaccines

We identified 15 studies reporting on vaccine data for pandemic influenza, and 11 studies for COVID-19 (Table 2). On vaccine dose frequency for pandemic influenza, five studies reported using two doses to fully vaccinate a person [104, 108, 128–130], while two studies from the United States reported one dose with maximum efficacy obtained after two weeks [28, 131]. Vaccination rate, defined as the number of vaccines administered per hour or persons vaccinated per hour, was reported in two studies: one at the rate of 17.5 vaccines per vaccinator per hour [128], based on an exercise carried out by a public health service, and the other at the rate of 30 per hour [132], based on guidelines set by the US Centres for

Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Manufacturing capacity for vaccines was reported on in two ways: first as the time it takes to develop a new vaccine (at least 6 months [133]) and second as capacity in doses per week (22 million monovalent doses globally, egg-based vaccine technology in 2004 [129]). Vaccine efficacy was also reported on in various ways for pandemic influenza: as reduction in chest X-rays (50%) and duration of antibiotic treatment (58% shorter) [134], as susceptibility (59–87%) [24, 135–137], as reduction of infectiousness (35–40%) [131, 136] and as reduction of illness given infection (80%) [131]. Two studies also reported on vaccine stockpiles for pandemic influenza (stockpiling for 30% of the population [132] with expected shelf-life of 4 years [138]). For COVID-19, five studies reported on vaccine efficacy. One study reported effectiveness of two doses BNT162b2 against of asymptomatic (0.49) or symptomatic infection (0.59) with the delta variant [139]. Data on vaccine efficacy of different vaccine types were identified as 94.6–95% for Pfizer/BioNTech [140, 141], 93.6% for Moderna [140], 60% for Moderna [140] and 65.8–67% for Janssen, single dose [140–142]. One study reports on the vaccine effectiveness of various combinations and doses against the delta variant: two doses CoronaVac and one dose BNT162b2: 98%, two doses CoronaVac and one dose ChAdOx1 nCoV-19: 86%, two doses ChAdOx1 nCoV-19: 83%, one dose CoronaVac+one dose ChAdOx1 nCoV-19: 74%, two doses CoronaVac: 60%; one dose of either CoronaVac or ChAdOx1 nCoV-19: <50% [143]. One study reported on vaccine effectiveness against transmission (VET) of primary BNT162b2 vaccination of 96% against the alpha variant, 87% against delta and 31% against omicron; and VET of booster vaccination was 87% against delta and 68% against omicron, decreasing to 71% (delta) and 55% (omicron) 150–200 days after booster vaccination [144]. One study also reports a breakthrough transmission rate of 10.1% from fully vaccinated patients to close contacts compared to 37.8% breakthrough transmission in the control group of unvaccinated patients to close contacts [145]. Five studies report on vaccination rates for COVID-19 during rollout of the vaccination campaigns in 2021. One study reports 0.27 doses per 100 people in Oman, 0.39 doses per 100 in Saudi Arabia, 3.92 doses per 100 people in Bahrain and 8.27 doses per 100 people in the United Arab Emirates [146]. Four studies report on the total amount of vaccinations administered per day: 4024 per day in the Basque Country, Spain [140]; up to 50,000 per day in Cambodia [147]; 1284 per day in Djibouti [148] and 42,249 per day in South Korea [149].

Testing and contact tracing

Studies on testing and contact tracing of people as a resource were only identified for COVID-19, totalling 19 studies, 16 on testing and three on contact tracing

(Supplementary Table 2). Resource parameters for testing were processing time in laboratories (5 h for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) tests) [150] and time to test result (<24 h from sample taking to delivery of test result for PCR or antigen tests [151, 152]) and test sensitivity (0.95–0.99 for PCR [150, 152–154] and 0.50–0.80 for lateral flow antigen (LFA) tests [152, 153, 155, 156]) and specificity (0.99 for PCR [154], 0.98–0.99 for LFA tests [152, 155, 156]). One study also reported on sensitivity of LFA tests in specific situations: 55.7% for the alpha variant, 64% for delta and 73% for omicron; 57.3% in case of unvaccinated individuals, 67.6% for those with one dose and 69.7% for those with two or more vaccine doses; and 68.7% in symptomatic cases vs. 52.8% in asymptomatic cases [156]. Amounts of tests performed were reported either as total amounts per 100,000 population (17.6–217 [150, 157, 158]), or number of tests per day, for PCR testing (137–2000000 per day, settings ranging from a mobile container testing facility to the United States [40, 85, 147, 148, 151, 152, 159–161]) or LFA testing (28–3002 per day, settings ranging from a mobile container testing facility to the Veteran's Health Administration [40, 151, 161]).

For contact tracing, adherence to contact tracing measures (18.2% full adherence to isolation) [153] was reported in one study. Two studies reported on the success rate of contact tracing, reporting either success of reaching contacts (99.5% within same day for household contacts, 85% within two days for school place contacts, 60% within two days for workplace contacts, 10% within three days for community contacts [162]) or other aspects of contact tracing (cases interviewed: 49%, interviewed cases who named contacts: 25%, contacts who were notified: 59%, contacts who were monitored: 32% [163]). This last study also reported on the speed of contact tracing, with it taking 3.5 days from testing to a case interview, and 4 days from testing to contact notification [163].

Discussion

This systematic review identified public health and healthcare resources with their associated parameters and values reported in relation to the pandemic influenza and COVID-19 pandemics. We found 147 studies, 45 related to pandemic influenza and 102 related to COVID-19, and identified 16 resource types and 48 resource parameters. As nearly 70% of the studies included were performed in hospitals, we found more resources related to healthcare than to public health. The data identified in this review will be of great benefit to resource modelling for preparedness and outbreak management because relevant model outputs rely on realistic input data. For preparedness activities, this will allow pandemic planners and policy makers to improve estimations for resource needs and stockpiles in preparedness plans and support

simulation-based training. For outbreak or pandemic management, more accurate short-term forecasting will better inform decision making for outbreak management policy and containment measures, both at public health and clinical level.

Most studies identified were on ICU and non-ICU bed-related resources, followed by mechanical ventilation and vaccines. All studies on testing and tracing were in relation to COVID-19, as testing and tracing were cornerstones of the measures to control COVID-19 and contact tracing was mainly used only in the initial containment phase of the influenza pandemic. The repeated searches showed growth in the body of work on testing, contact tracing, vaccines and pharmaceuticals as a resource relevant to COVID-19. This was expected as the understanding of COVID-19 vaccines and pharmaceutical treatment grew over the course of the pandemic, with vaccines being rolled out beginning 2021. Testing schemes also gained traction over the course of the year 2021, with many countries requiring proof of vaccination or negative COVID-19 status on entry or for public venues.

While this is a comprehensive overview, it is by no means exhaustive. Bayram et al. [164] published a Delphi study on critical care resources in 2013, listing 58 different resources possibly required for critical care of pandemic influenza. Data on the availability or consumption of such specific resources as needles, blood pressure cuffs or intravenous pumps will generally not be published in scientific studies but may be known to hospital management. Non-PPE consumables are critical for delivery of care and shortages have occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic [165] so ensuring sufficient stock should be a priority for pandemic planners. However, such resources may be too specific and omitted from resource models to avoid excessive complexity.

This study has multiple strengths. The diverse backgrounds of researchers involved in this study ensured that perspectives from public health, healthcare (primary care and internal medicine), epidemiology, infection prevention and control, and mathematical modelling were all represented in the design and execution of this study. This study was conducted as part of the PANDEM-2 project, which included resource modelling work, ensuring practical application of the findings such as in a functional exercise [12].

The search strategy is, however, also one of the limitations of this study. As we chose to search for resources in the context of a pandemic, certain resources or resource parameters may not have been identified in this study because publications on those resources were not pandemic-related. The search did not include terms specific for prophylactic or therapeutic drugs. This is a limitation and may have caused under-inclusion of studies on prophylactic or therapeutic drugs if they did not contain

other keywords present in our search strategy. Reviews on therapy for pandemic influenza and COVID-19 are widely available [166–171]. Only three studies on contact tracing were included in this review. While we identified more studies on contact tracing, the main focus of these studies was investigating contact tracing as a non-pharmaceutical intervention (NPI) and its effect on reducing morbidity and mortality. We also did not include grey literature or policy documents in this study, which could contain information on resources that is not published scientifically. Users of the data collected in this study should also be aware of the highly diverse context in which these studies are performed, with regional context, population characteristics and timing of the study in relation to pandemic phases being important factors. The final repeat of our search identified a number of reviews on COVID-19 vaccines and diagnostic tests [172–176]. We elected not to include the articles reviewed therein in our work as our aim was to provide an overview of available resource data and not an in-depth review on the efficacy of COVID-19 vaccines or tests.

Conclusion

In this review, we identified a broad range of public health and healthcare resources and their corresponding parameters that have been published in relation to the 2009 influenza A(H1N1) and COVID-19 pandemics. Each pandemic comes with its own unexpected and unforeseen challenges, caused by specific features related to the pathogen and the disease, but also can be related to the global or geopolitical context at that time, which may impact the availability and accessibility of resources needed for pandemic response. Nevertheless, the data gathered in this study will provide valuable input for resource modelling work and may also be of use to policy makers and pandemic planners. Hospital resources such as non-ICU beds, ICU beds, mechanical ventilation and healthcare staff, vaccines and PPE are well described in scientific literature, while for other resources such as contact tracing, general practitioners and home care, limited data on capacity and use is currently available in scientific literature. More research on mapping the availability and use of these resources would be of great value for preparing for future pandemics by allowing the creation of more realistic scenarios and estimates for resource needs in order to prevent resource shortages and disruption to critical care delivery. Future research could also use the data gathered in this review to estimate required stockpiling of healthcare resources for future pandemics, and to determine the size of pandemic emergency funds needed to cover resource requirements. This will especially apply to potential future pandemics, when countries might find themselves facing shortages of resources. Therefore detailed pandemic planning would contribute

health system resilience when the next pandemic confronts us in the future.

Supplementary Information

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Supplementary Material 1

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Author contributions

MS, ATi and MC conceived the study; BB, MS, ATo, CR and ATi designed the study. BB and JB collected and analyzed the data. BB, JB, MS, ATo, CR and ATi interpreted the data. BB drafted the manuscript, MS, JB, ATo, CG, JD, MC, CR and ATi critically reviewed the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

All data included in this study are reported in the article or uploaded as supplementary information.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable. This study is a systematic review of existing literature on public health and healthcare resources. No subjects were enrolled in this study. Patients or members of the public were not involved in the development of the research question or choice of outcome measures.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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References

- Guan D, Wang D, Hallegatte S, Davis SJ, Huo J, Li S, et al. Global supply-chain effects of COVID-19 control measures. *Nat Hum Behav.* 2020;4(6):577–87.
- Wu H, Soe MM, Konnor R, Dantes R, Haass K, Dudeck MA et al. Hospital capacities and shortages of healthcare resources among US hospitals during the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, National Healthcare Safety Network (NHSN), March 27–July 14, 2020. *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology.* 2021:1–4.
- Zhang L, Chai L, Zhao Y, Wang L, Sun W, Lu L, et al. Burnout in nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic in China: new challenges for public health. *Biosci Trends.* 2021;15(2):129–31.
- Cohen J, van der Meulen Rodgers Y. Contributing factors to personal protective equipment shortages during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Prev Med.* 2020;141:106263.
- Entress RM, Tyler J, Sadiq AA. Managing mass fatalities during COVID-19: lessons for promoting community resilience during global pandemics. *Public Adm Rev.* 2020;80(5):856–61.

6. Grassly NC, Fraser C. Mathematical models of infectious disease transmission. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2008;6(6):477–87.
7. Currie CS, Fowler JW, Kotiadis K, Monks T, Onggo BS, Robertson DA, Tako AA. How simulation modelling can help reduce the impact of COVID-19. *J Simul.* 2020;14(2):83–97.
8. Belfroid E, Robetakamp D, Fraser G, Swaan C, Timen A. Towards defining core principles of public health emergency preparedness: scoping review and Delphi consultation among European Union country experts. *BMC Public Health.* 2020;20(1):1482.
9. Bozzani FM, Vassall A, Gomez GB. Building resource constraints and feasibility considerations in mathematical models for infectious disease: a systematic literature review. *Epidemics.* 2021;35.
10. Klein MG, Cheng CJ, Lii E, Mao K, Mesbahi H, Zhu T et al. COVID-19 Models for Hospital Surge Capacity Planning: A Systematic Review. *Disaster medicine and public health preparedness.* 2020;1–17.
11. CORDIS. Pandemic Preparedness and Response Brussels: European Commission. 2021 [<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/883285>]
12. Green C, Beishuizen B, Stein M, Rovers CP, Tostmann A, de Jong DL et al. Using system dynamics to support a functional exercise for pandemic preparedness and response. *Syst Dynamics Rev.* 2024:e1786.
13. Van Der Weijden CP, Stein ML, Jacobi AJ, Kretzschmar MEE, Reintjes R, van Steenberghe JE, Timen A. Choosing pandemic parameters for pandemic preparedness planning: a comparison of pandemic scenarios prior to and following the influenza A(H1N1) 2009 pandemic. *Health Policy.* 2013;109(1):52–62.
14. Liberati A, Altman DG, Tetzlaff J, Mulrow C, Gøtzsche PC, Ioannidis JP, et al. The PRISMA statement for reporting systematic reviews and meta-analyses of studies that evaluate health care interventions: explanation and elaboration. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2009;62(10):e1–34.
15. Pollock D, Peters MD, Khalil H, McInerney P, Alexander L, Tricco AC, et al. Recommendations for the extraction, analysis, and presentation of results in scoping reviews. *JBI Evid Synthesis.* 2023;21(3):520–32.
16. The EndNote Team. *EndNote.* EndNote 20 ed. Philadelphia, PA: Clarivate; 2013.
17. Fantom NJ, Serajuddin U. The World Bank's classification of countries by income. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper.* 2016(7528).
18. CORDIS. Health system analysis to support capacity development to respond to pandemic influenza in Asia Brussels: European Union. 2019 [<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/201823>]
19. Chu C, Lee J, Choi DH, Youn SK, Lee JK. Sensitivity analysis of the parameters of Korea's pandemic influenza preparedness plan. *Osong Public Health Res Perspect.* 2011;2(3):210–5.
20. Fort D, Seoane L, Unis GD, Price-Haywood EG. Locally informed modeling to predict hospital and intensive care unit capacity during the COVID-19 epidemic. *Ochsner J.* 2020;20(3):285–92.
21. Huang HC, Araz OM, Morton DP, Johnson GP, Damien P, Clements B, Meyers LA. Stockpiling ventilators for influenza pandemics. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2017;23(6):914–21.
22. Lee BY, McGlone SM, Bailey RR, Wiringa AE, Zimmer SM, Smith KJ, Zimmerman RK. To test or to treat? An analysis of influenza testing and antiviral treatment strategies using economic computer modeling. *PLoS ONE.* 2010;5(6).
23. Smetanin P, Stiff D, Kumar A, Kobak P, Zarychanski R, Simonsen N, Plummer F. Potential intensive care unit ventilator demand/capacity mismatch due to novel swine-origin H1N1 in Canada. *Can J Infect Dis Med Microbiol.* 2009;20(4):e115–23.
24. Tuite AR, Fisman DN, Kwong JC, Greer AL. Optimal pandemic influenza vaccine allocation strategies for the Canadian population. *PLoS ONE.* 2010;5(5).
25. Nap RE, Andriessen MPH, Meessen NEL, Van Der Werf TS. Pandemic influenza and hospital resources. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2007;13(11):1714–9.
26. Abramovich MN, Hershey JC, Callies B, Adalja AA, Tosh PK, Toner ES. Hospital influenza pandemic stockpiling needs: a computer simulation. *Am J Infect Control.* 2017;45(3):272–7.
27. Irvine N, Anderson G, Sinha C, McCabe H, van der Meer R. Collaborative critical care prediction and resource planning during the COVID-19 pandemic using computer simulation modelling: future urgent planning lessons. *Future Healthc J.* 2021;8(2):E317–21.
28. Miller G, Randolph S, Patterson JE. Responding to simulated pandemic influenza in San Antonio, Texas. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol.* 2008;29(4):320–6.
29. Ten Eyck RP. Ability of regional hospitals to meet projected avian flu pandemic surge capacity requirements. *Prehospital and disaster medicine: the official journal of the National Association of EMS Physicians and the World Association for Emergency and Disaster Medicine in association with the Acute Care Foundation.* 2008;23(2):103–12.
30. Zhang X, Meltzer MI, Wortley PM. FluSurge - A tool to estimate demand for hospital services during the next pandemic influenza. *Med Decis Making.* 2006;26(6):617–23.
31. Nuño M, Chowell G, Gumel AB. Assessing the role of basic control measures, antivirals and vaccine in curtailing pandemic influenza: scenarios for the US, UK and the Netherlands. *J Royal Soc Interface.* 2007;4(14):505–21.
32. Van Genugten MLL, Heijnen MLA. The expected number of hospitalisations and beds needed due to pandemic influenza on a regional level in the Netherlands. *Virus Res.* 2004;103(1–2):17–23.
33. Barrett K, Khan YA, Mbiotech SM, Ximenes R, Naimark DMJ, Sander B. Estimation of covid-19 induced depletion of hospital resources in Ontario, Canada. *CMAJ.* 2020;192(24):E640–6.
34. Booton RD, Macgregor L, Vass L, Looker KJ, Hyams C, Bright PD et al. Estimating the COVID-19 epidemic trajectory and hospital capacity requirements in South West England: a mathematical modelling framework. *BMJ Open.* 2021;11(1).
35. Giannakeas V, Bhatia D, Warkentin MT, Bogoch II, Stall NM. Estimating the Maximum Capacity of COVID-19 cases manageable per day given a Health Care System's Constrained resources. *Ann Intern Med.* 2020;173(5):407–10.
36. Verma VR, Saini A, Gandhi S, Dash U, Koya SF. Capacity-need gap in hospital resources for varying mitigation and containment strategies in India in the face of COVID-19 pandemic. *Infect Disease Modelling.* 2020;5:608–21.
37. Iragorri N, Gómez-Restrepo C, Barrett K, Herrera S, Hurtado I, Khan Y, et al. COVID-19: adaptation of a model to predicting healthcare resources needs in Valle Del Cauca, Colombia. *Colombia Medica.* (Cali Colombia). 2020;51(3):e204534.
38. Kasturi SN, Park J, Wild D, Khan B, Haggstrom DA, Grannis S. Predicting COVID-19-related health care resource utilization across a statewide patient population: model development study. *J Med Internet Res.* 2021;23(11).
39. Ruggeri M, Signorini A, Caravaggio S, Rua J, Luís N, Braz S, Aragão F. Estimation model for Healthcare costs and Intensive Care Units Access for Covid-19 patients and evaluation of the effects of Remdesivir in the Portuguese context: hypothetical study. *Clin Drug Invest.* 2022;42(4):345–54.
40. Subiros M, De Latour CR, Parenton F, Soulaïmana I, Hassani Y, Blondé R et al. Epidemiological profile of COVID-19 in the French overseas department Mayotte, 2020 to 2021. *Eurosurveillance.* 2022;27(34).
41. Datta BK, Ansa BE, George V. An analytical model of population level chronic conditions and COVID-19 related hospitalization in the United States. *BMC Public Health.* 2022;22(1):208.
42. Pastorino R, Villani L, La Millia DI, Ieraci R, Chini F, Volpe E, et al. Influenza and pneumococcal vaccinations are not associated to COVID-19 outcomes among patients admitted to a university hospital. *Vaccine.* 2021;39(26):3493–7.
43. Suetens C, Kinross P, Berciano PG, Nebreda VA, Hassan E, Calba C et al. Increasing risk of breakthrough COVID-19 in outbreaks with high attack rates in European long-term care facilities, July to October 2021. *Eurosurveillance.* 2021;26(49).
44. Bagshaw SM, Abbott A, Beeson S, Bowker SL, Zuege DJ, Thanh NX. A population-based assessment of avoidable hospitalizations and resource use of non-vaccinated patients with COVID-19. *Canadian journal of public health = Revue canadienne de sante publique.* 2023.
45. Solanki G, Wilkinson T, Bansal S, Shiba J, Manda S, Doherty T. COVID-19 hospitalization and mortality and hospitalization-related utilization and expenditure: analysis of a South African private health insured population. *PLoS ONE.* 2022;17(5 May).
46. Weissman GE, Crane-Droesch A, Chivers C, Luong T, Hanish A, Levy MZ, et al. Locally informed Simulation to predict Hospital Capacity needs during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Ann Intern Med.* 2020;173(1):21–8.
47. Beatty K, Kavanagh PM. A retrospective cohort study of outcomes in hospitalised COVID-19 patients during the first pandemic wave in Ireland. *Ir J Med Sci.* 2021.
48. Castagna F, Xue X, Saeed O, Kataria R, Puius YA, Patel SR et al. Hospital bed occupancy rate is an independent risk factor for COVID-19 inpatient mortality: a pandemic epicentre cohort study. *BMJ Open.* 2022;12(2).
49. Dadhwal K, Stonham R, Breen H, Poole S, Saeed K, Dushianthan A. Severe COVID-19 pneumonia in an intensive care setting and comparisons with historic severe viral pneumonia due to other viruses. *Clin Respiratory J.* 2022.
50. Hayden E, Airoldi C, Scotti L, Bellan M, Sottosanti A, Bergamasco P, et al. Modelling hospital bed necessity for COVID-19 patients during the decline phase of the epidemic trajectory. *Minerva Respiratory Med.* 2021;60(2):29–35.

51. Pham TM, Tahir H, van de Wijgert JHHM, Van der Roest BR, Ellerbroek P, Bonten MJM et al. Interventions to control nosocomial transmission of SARS-CoV-2: a modelling study. *BMC Med.* 2021;19(1).
52. Tran Kiem C, Bosetti P, Paireau J, Crépey P, Salje H, Lefrancq N et al. SARS-CoV-2 transmission across age groups in France and implications for control. *Nat Commun.* 2021;12(1).
53. Scott A, Chambers R, Reimbaeva M, Atwell J, Baillon-Plot N, Draica F, Tarallo M. Real-world retrospective analysis of patient characteristics, healthcare resource utilization, costs, and treatment patterns among unvaccinated adults with COVID-19 diagnosed in outpatient settings in the United States. *J Med Econ.* 2022;25(1):287–98.
54. Haase N, Plovsing R, Christensen S, Poulsen LM, Brøchner AC, Rasmussen BS, et al. Changes over time in characteristics, resource use and outcomes among ICU patients with COVID-19—A nationwide, observational study in Denmark. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand.* 2022;66(8):987–95.
55. Philips S, Shi Y, Coopersmith CM, Samuels OB, Pimentel-Farias C, Mei Y, et al. Surge Capacity in the COVID-19 era: a natural experiment of Neurocritical Care in General critical care. *Neurocrit Care.* 2023;38(2):320–5.
56. Ruggeri M, Signorini A, Caravaggio S, Alraddadi B, Alali A, Jarrett J, et al. Modeling the potential impact of Remdesivir Treatment for hospitalized patients with COVID-19 in Saudi Arabia on Healthcare Resource Use and Direct Hospital costs: a hypothetical study. *Clin Drug Investig.* 2022;42(8):669–78.
57. Trentini F, Marziano V, Guzzetta G, Tirani M, Cereda D, Poletti P, et al. Pressure on the health-care system and intensive care utilization during the COVID-19 outbreak in the Lombardy Region of Italy: a retrospective observational study in 43,538 hospitalized patients. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2022;191(1):137–46.
58. Melman GJ, Parlikad AK, Cameron EAB. Balancing scarce hospital resources during the COVID-19 pandemic using discrete-event simulation. *Health Care Manag Sci.* 2021;24(2):356–74.
59. Hohl CM, Rosychuk RJ, Hau JP, Hayward J, Landes M, Yan JW, et al. Treatments, resource utilization, and outcomes of COVID-19 patients presenting to emergency departments across pandemic waves: an observational study by the Canadian COVID-19 Emergency Department Rapid Response Network (CCEDRRN). *Can J Emerg Med.* 2022;24(4):397–407.
60. Stepanova M, Lam B, Younossi E, Felix S, Ziaee M, Price J et al. The impact of variants and vaccination on the mortality and resource utilization of hospitalized patients with COVID-19. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2022;22(1).
61. Baker PRA, Sun J, Morris J, Dines A. Epidemiologic modeling with Flusurge for pandemic (H1N1) 2009 outbreak, Queensland, Australia. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2011;17(9):1608–14.
62. Ercole A, Taylor BL, Rhodes A, Menon DK. Modelling the impact of an influenza A/H1N1 pandemic on critical care demand from early pathogenicity data: the case for sentinel reporting. *Anaesthesia.* 2009;64(9):937–41.
63. Galante M, Garin O, Sicuri E, Cots F, García-Altés A, Ferrer M et al. Health services utilization, work absenteeism and costs of pandemic influenza A (H1N1) 2009 in Spain: a multicenter-longitudinal study. *PLoS ONE.* 2012;7(2).
64. Stiff D, Kumar A, Kisson N, Fowler R, Jovet P, Skippen P, et al. Potential pediatric intensive care unit demand/capacity mismatch due to novel pH1N1 in Canada. *Pediatr Crit Care Med.* 2011;12(2):e51–7.
65. Balicer RD, Huerta M, Davidovitch N, Grotto I. Cost-benefit of stockpiling drugs for influenza pandemic. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2005;11(8):1280–2.
66. Nicolay N, Callaghan MA, Domegan LM, Oza AN, Marsh BJ, Flanagan PC, et al. Epidemiology, clinical characteristics and resource implications of pandemic (H1N1) 2009 in intensive care units in Ireland. *Crit Care Resuscitation: J Australasian Acad Crit Care Med.* 2010;12(4):255–61.
67. Elhadi M, Alsoufi A, Abusalama A, Alkaseek A, Abdeewi S, Yahya M et al. Epidemiology, outcomes, and utilization of intensive care unit resources for critically ill COVID-19 patients in Libya: a prospective multi-center cohort study. *PLoS ONE.* 2021;16(4 April).
68. Ghaffar AE, Salem MM, Al Soda MR, Abd El Razik MF, Tahoon MS, Tahoon MH. COVID-19 pandemic preparedness in Egypt's teaching hospitals: a needs Assessment Study. *Front Public Health.* 2021;9:748666.
69. Ravikumar N, Nallasamy K, Bansal A, Angurana SK, Basavaraja GV, Sundaram M, et al. Novel coronavirus 2019 (2019-nCoV) infection: part I - preparedness and management in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit in Resource-limited settings. *Indian Pediatr.* 2020;57(4):324–34.
70. Mayorga L, García Samartino C, Flores G, Masuelli S, Sánchez MV, Mayorga LS, Sánchez CG. A modelling study highlights the power of detecting and isolating asymptomatic or very mildly affected individuals for COVID-19 epidemic management. *BMC Public Health.* 2020;20(1):1809.
71. Gelfman LP, Moreno J, Frydman JL, Singer J, Houldsworth J, Cordon-Cardo C et al. Characteristics Associated With Disparities Among Older Adults in Coronavirus Disease 2019 Outcomes in an Academic Health Care System. *Medical care.* 2022.
72. Richardson S, Hirsch JS, Narasimhan M, Crawford JM, McGinn T, Davidson KW, et al. Presenting characteristics, comorbidities, and outcomes among 5700 patients hospitalized with COVID-19 in the New York City area. *JAMA.* 2020;323(20):2052–9.
73. Avelino-Silva VI, Avelino-Silva TJ, Aliberti MJR, Ferreira JC, Cobello Junior V, Silva KR et al. Prediction of intensive care admission and hospital mortality in COVID-19 patients using demographics and baseline laboratory data. *Clinics.* 2023;78.
74. Boussarsar M, Meddeb K, Toumi R, Ennouri E, Ayed S, Jarraya F, et al. Resource utilization and preparedness within the COVID-19 pandemic in Tunisian medical intensive care units: a nationwide retrospective multicentre observational study. *J Infect Public Health.* 2023;16(5):727–35.
75. Moon RC, Brown H, Rosenthal N. Healthcare Resource utilization of patients with COVID-19 visiting US hospitals. *Value Health.* 2022;25(5):751–60.
76. Rennert-May E, Crocker A, D'Souza AG, Zhang Z, Chew D, Beall R et al. Health-care utilization and adverse outcomes stratified by sex, age and long-term care residency using the Alberta COVID-19 analytics and Research Database (ACARD): a population-based descriptive study. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2023;23(1).
77. Bagshaw SM, Abbott A, Beeson S, Zuege DJ, Wasylak T, Manns B, Nguyen TX. Avoidable intensive care unit resource use and costs of unvaccinated patients with COVID-19: a historical population-based cohort study Utilisation et coûts évitables des ressources des unités de soins intensifs pour les patients non vaccinés atteints de COVID-19: une étude de cohorte historique basée sur la population. *Can J Anesth.* 2022;69(11):1399–404.
78. Laake JH, Buanes EA, Småstuen MC, Kvåle R, Olsen BF, Rustøen T, et al. Characteristics, management and survival of ICU patients with coronavirus disease-19 in Norway, March-June 2020. A prospective observational study. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand.* 2021;65(5):618–28.
79. Wood RM, McWilliams CJ, Thomas MJ, Bourdeaux CP, Vasilakis C. COVID-19 scenario modelling for the mitigation of capacity-dependent deaths in intensive care. *Health Care Manag Sci.* 2020;23(3):315–24.
80. Bartoszko J, Dranitsaris G, Wilcox ME, Del Sorbo L, Mehta S, Peer M, et al. Development of a repeated-measures predictive model and clinical risk score for mortality in ventilated COVID-19 patients Mise Au point D'un modèle prédictif à mesures répétées et d'un score de risque clinique de mortalité pour les patients COVID-19 ventilés. *Can J Anesth.* 2022;69(3):343–52.
81. Lam SSW, Pourghaderi AR, Abdullah HR, Nguyen FNHL, Siddiqui FJ, Ansah JP, et al. An Agile systems modeling Framework for Bed Resource Planning during COVID-19 pandemic in Singapore. *Front Public Health.* 2022;10:714092.
82. Abdullah HR, Lam SSW, Ang BY, Pourghaderi A, Nguyen FNHL, Matchar DB et al. Resuming elective surgery after COVID-19: a simulation modelling framework for guiding the phased opening of operating rooms. *Int J Med Informatics.* 2022;158.
83. Hertzberg D, Renberg M, Nyman J, Bell M, Rimes Stigare C. Experiences of renal replacement therapy delivery in Swedish intensive care units during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Blood Purif.* 2021:1–6.
84. Berger E, Winkelmann J, Eckhardt H, Nimpitsch U, Panteli D, Reichebner C, et al. A country-level analysis comparing hospital capacity and utilisation during the first COVID-19 wave across Europe. *Health Policy.* 2022;126(5):373–81.
85. Prada SI, Garcia-Garcia MP, Guzman J. COVID-19 response in Colombia: hits and misses. *Health Policy Technol.* 2022;11(2).
86. Vidal-Cortés P, Martín MC, Díaz E, Bodí M, Igeño JC, Garnacho-Montero J. Impact of one year of pandemic on Spanish intensive care units Impacto De Un año de pandemia en las Unidades De Cuidados Intensivos De España. *Revista Esp De Quimioterapia.* 2022;35(4):392–400.
87. Challen K, Bentley A, Bright J, Walter D. Clinical review: Mass casualty triage - pandemic influenza and critical care. *Crit Care.* 2007;11(2).
88. Krumkamp R, Kretzschmar M, Rudge JW, Ahmad A, Hanvoravongchai P, Westenhofer J, et al. Health service resource needs for pandemic influenza in developing countries: a linked transmission dynamics, interventions and resource demand model. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2011;139(1):59–67.
89. Stein ML, Rudge JW, Coker R, van der Weijden C, Krumkamp R, Hanvoravongchai P, et al. Development of a resource modelling tool to support decision makers in pandemic influenza preparedness: the AsiaFluCap Simulator. *BMC Public Health.* 2012;12:870.
90. Cummings MJ, Baldwin MR, Abrams D, Jacobson SD, Meyer BJ, Balough EM, et al. Epidemiology, clinical course, and outcomes of critically ill adults with COVID-19 in New York City: a prospective cohort study. *Lancet.* 2020;395(10239):1763–70.

91. Bae J, Kapse S, Singh G, Gattu R, Ali S, Shah N et al. Predicting mechanical ventilation and mortality in covid-19 using radiomics and deep learning on chest radiographs: a multi-institutional study. *Diagnostics*. 2021;11(10).
92. Kafan S, Vajargah KT, Sheikhhvatan M, Tabrizi G, Salimzadeh A, Montazeri M et al. Predicting risk score for mechanical ventilation in hospitalized adult patients suffering from covid-19. *Anesthesiology Pain Med*. 2021;11(2).
93. McCabe R, Kont MD, Schmit N, Whittaker C, Løchen A, Baguelin M, et al. Modelling intensive care unit capacity under different epidemiological scenarios of the COVID-19 pandemic in three western European countries. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2021;50(3):753–67.
94. Islam MS, Bhowmick DK, Parveen M, Kamal MM, Akhtaruzzaman AKM. Case fatality rate and survival functions of severe COVID-19 patients in intensive care unit of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University in Bangladesh: An observational study. *Anaesthesia, Pain and Intensive Care*. 2021;25(4):443–9.
95. Grasselli G, Zangrillo A, Zanella A, Antonelli M, Cabrini L, Castelli A, et al. Baseline characteristics and outcomes of 1591 patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 admitted to ICUs of the Lombardy Region, Italy. *JAMA*. 2020;323(16):1574–81.
96. Nap RE, Andriessen MPH, Meessen NEL, Dos Reis Miranda D, Van Der Werf TS. Pandemic influenza and excess intensive-care workload. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2008;14(10):1518–25.
97. Considine J, Shaban RZ, Patrick J, Holzhauser K, Aitken P, Clark M, et al. Pandemic (H1N1) 2009 Influenza in Australia: absenteeism and redeployment of emergency medicine and nursing staff. *EMA - Emerg Med Australasia*. 2011;23(5):615–23.
98. Oakley C, Pascoe C, Balthazor D, Bennett D, Gautam N, Isaac J et al. Assembly Line ICU: what the Long shops taught us about managing surge capacity for COVID-19. *BMJ open Qual*. 2020;9(4).
99. Beijaert RPH, Numans ME. Uitval Van huisartsenzorg door covid-19-vaccin Leerpunten Voor toekomstige vaccinatierondes. *Ned Tijdschr Geneesk*. 2021;165(37).
100. Adisasmito W, Hunter BM, Krumkamp R, Latief K, Rudge JW, Hanvoravongchai P, Coker RJ. Pandemic influenza and health system resource gaps in Bali: an analysis through a resource transmission dynamics model. *Asia-Pac J Public Health/Asia-Pac Acad Consort Public Health*. 2015;27(2):NP713–33.
101. Chen C, Luo Q, Chong N, Westergaard S, Brantley E, Salsberg E, et al. Coronavirus disease 2019 planning and response: a tale of 2 Health Workforce Estimator Tools. *Med Care*. 2021;59:S420–7.
102. Chomton M, Marsac L, Deho A, Maroni A, Geslain G, Frannais-Haverland K, et al. Transforming a paediatric ICU to an adult ICU for severe Covid-19: lessons learned. *Eur J Pediatrics*. 2021;180(7):2319–23.
103. Ang B, Archuleta S, Chiew YF, Chlebicki MP, Chua A, Fisher DA, et al. Management of novel influenza epidemics in Singapore: Consensus recommendations from the Hospital Influenza Workgroup (Singapore). *Singapore Med J*. 2009;50(6):567–80.
104. Doyle A, Bonmarin I, Lévy-Bruhl D, Le Strat Y, Desenclos JC. Influenza pandemic preparedness in France: modelling the impact of interventions. *J Epidemiol Commun Health*. 2006;60(5):399–404.
105. Lee VJ, Chen MI. Effectiveness of neuraminidase inhibitors for preventing staff absenteeism during pandemic influenza. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2007;13(3):449–57.
106. Lee BY, Bailey RR, Wiringa AE, Assi TM, Beigi RH. Antiviral medications for pregnant women for pandemic and seasonal influenza: an economic computer model. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2009;114(5):971–80.
107. Opstelten W, Van Steenbergen JE, Van Essen GA, Van Der Sande MAB. The use of antiviral agents during an (impending) influenza pandemic het gebruik van antivirale middelen tijdens een (dreigende) influenzapandemie. *Ned Tijdschr Geneesk*. 2007;151(18):1008–12.
108. Sander B, Nizam A, Garrison LP Jr, Postma MJ, Halloran ME, Longini IM Jr. Economic evaluation of influenza pandemic mitigation strategies in the United States using a stochastic microsimulation transmission model. *Value Health*. 2009;12(2):226–33.
109. Merler S, Ajelli M, Rizzo C. Age-prioritized use of antivirals during an influenza pandemic. *BMC Infect Dis*. 2009;9.
110. Chua BWB, Huynh VA, Lou J, Goh FT, Clapham H, Teerawattananon Y, Wee HL. Protocol for the economic evaluation of COVID-19 pandemic response policies. *BMJ Open*. 2021;11(9).
111. Wang Y, Zhang D, Du G, Du R, Zhao J, Jin Y, et al. Remdesivir in adults with severe COVID-19: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicentre trial. *Lancet*. 2020;395(10236):1569–78.
112. Lawandi A, Warner S, Sun J, Demirkale CY, Danner RL, Klompas M, et al. Suspected severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) reinfections: incidence, predictors, and Healthcare Use among patients at 238 US Healthcare Facilities, 1 June 2020 to 28 February 2021. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2022;74(8):1489–92.
113. Chappell L, Horby P, Lim W, The RECOVERY Collaborative Group. Dexamethasone in hospitalized patients with Covid-19. *N Engl J Med*. 2020;384(8):693–704.
114. Doron S, Monach PA, Brown CM, Branch-Elliman W. Improving COVID-19 Disease Severity Surveillance Measures: Statewide Implementation Experience. *Annals of internal medicine*. 2023.
115. Mahévas M, Tran V-T, Roumier M, Chabrol A, Paule R, Guillaud C et al. Clinical efficacy of hydroxychloroquine in patients with covid-19 pneumonia who require oxygen: observational comparative study using routine care data. *BMJ*. 2020;369.
116. Rosenberg ES, Dufort EM, Udo T, Wilberschied LA, Kumar J, Tesoriero J, et al. Association of treatment with hydroxychloroquine or azithromycin with in-hospital mortality in patients with COVID-19 in New York State. *JAMA*. 2020;323(24):2493–502.
117. Hashikura M, Kizu J. Stockpile of personal protective equipment in hospital settings: preparedness for influenza pandemics. *Am J Infect Control*. 2009;37(9):703–7.
118. Phin NF, Rylands AJ, Allan J, Edwards C, Enstone JE, Nguyen-Van-Tam JS. Personal protective equipment in an influenza pandemic: a UK simulation exercise. *J Hosp Infect*. 2009;71(1):15–21.
119. Swaminathan A, Martin R, Gamon S, Abolins C, Athan E, Braitberg G, et al. Personal protective equipment and antiviral drug use during hospitalization for suspected avian or pandemic influenza. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2007;13(10):1541–7.
120. Abedrabboh K, Pilz M, Al-Fagih Z, Al-Fagih OS, Nebel JC, Al-Fagih L. Game theory to enhance stock management of personal protective equipment (PPE) during the COVID-19 outbreak. *PLoS ONE*. 2021;16(2 February).
121. Khawaja SN, Qadri HA, Yusuf MA. Cancer hospital stockpiles: strategizing for an efficient and sufficient inventory list of essential items. *JCO Global Oncol*. 2021(7):1490–9.
122. Baldi E, Sechi GM, Mare C, Canevari F, Brancaglione A, Primi R, et al. Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest during the COVID-19 outbreak in Italy. *N Engl J Med*. 2020;383(5):496–8.
123. Jost D, Derkenne C, Kedzierewicz R, Briche F, Frattini B, Bertho K, et al. The need to adapt the rescue chain for out-of-hospital cardiac arrest during the COVID-19 pandemic: experience from the Paris Fire Brigade Basic Life Support and Advanced Life Support teams. *Resuscitation*. 2020;153:56–7.
124. Marijon E, Karam N, Jost D, Perrot D, Frattini B, Derkenne C, et al. Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest during the COVID-19 pandemic in Paris, France: a population-based, observational study. *Lancet Public Health*. 2020;5(8):e437–43.
125. Methi F, Hernæs KH, Skyrud KD, Magnusson K. Pandemic trends in health care use: from the hospital bed to self-care with COVID-19. *PLoS ONE*. 2022;17(3 March).
126. Chalk D, Robbins S, Kandasamy R, Rush K, Aggarwal A, Sullivan R, Chamberlain C. Modelling palliative and end-of-life resource requirements during COVID-19: implications for quality care. *BMJ Open*. 2021;11(5).
127. Arya A, Buchman S, Gagnon B, Downar J. Pandemic palliative care: beyond ventilators and saving lives. *CMAJ*. 2020;192(15):E400–4.
128. Aaby K, Abbey RL, Herrmann JW, Treadwell M, Jordan CS, Wood K. Embracing computer modeling to address pandemic influenza in the 21st century. *J Public Health Manage Pract*. 2006;12(4):365–72.
129. Medema JK, Zoellner YF, Ryan J, Palache AM. Modeling pandemic preparedness scenarios: Health economic implications of enhanced pandemic vaccine supply. *Virus Res*. 2004;103(1–2):9–15.
130. Milne G, Kelso J, Kelly H. Strategies for mitigating an influenza pandemic with pre-pandemic H5N1 vaccines. *J Royal Soc Interface*. 2010;7(45):573–86.
131. Kasaie P, Kelton WD. Resource allocation for controlling epidemics: calibrating, analyzing, and optimizing an agent-based simulation. *IIE Trans Healthc Syst Eng*. 2013;3(2):94–109.
132. Cruz-Aponte M, McKiernan EC, Herrera-Valdez MA. Mitigating effects of vaccination on influenza outbreaks given constraints in stockpile size and daily administration capacity. *BMC Infect Dis*. 2011;11.
133. Lee HY, Oh MN, Park YS, Chu C, Son TJ. Public Health Crisis Preparedness and Response in Korea. *Osong Public Health Res Perspect*. 2013;4(5):278–84.
134. Hara Y, Hagihara A, Ikematu H, Nobutomo K. Efficacy of influenza vaccine among elderly patients by physical activity status. *Environ Health Prev Med*. 2002;7(5):183–8.
135. Ho PI, Liu W, Li TZR, Chan TC, Ku CC, Lien YH et al. Taiwan's Response to Influenza: A Seroepidemiological Evaluation of Policies and Implications for

- Pandemic Preparedness. International journal of infectious diseases: IJID : official publication of the International Society for Infectious Diseases. 2022.
136. Saunders-Hastings P, Hayes BQ, Smith R, Krewski D. National assessment of Canadian pandemic preparedness: employing InFluNet to identify high-risk areas for inter-wave vaccine distribution. *Infect Disease Modelling*. 2017;2(3):341–52.
 137. Wood J, McCaw J, Becker N, Nolan T, MacIntyre CR. Optimal dosing and dynamic distribution of vaccines in an influenza pandemic. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2009;169(12):1517–24.
 138. Godeaux O, Izurieta P, Madariaga M, Dramé M, Li P, Vaughn DW. Immunogenicity and safety of AS03 <inf>A-adjuvanted H5N1 influenza vaccine prepared from bulk antigen after stockpiling for 4 years. *Vaccine*. 2015;33(18):2189–95.
 139. de León UAP, Avila-Vales E, Huang K. Modeling the transmission of the SARS-CoV-2 Delta variant in a partially vaccinated Population. *Viruses*. 2022;14(1).
 140. Canga A, Bidegain G. Modelling the Effect of the Interaction between Vaccination and Nonpharmaceutical Measures on COVID-19 Incidence. *Global Health, Epidemiology and Genomics*. 2022;2022.
 141. Li Q, Huang Y. Optimizing global COVID-19 vaccine allocation: an agent-based computational model of 148 countries. *PLoS Comput Biol*. 2022;18(9).
 142. Taboe HB, Asare-Baah M, Iboi EA, Ngonghala CN. Critical assessment of the impact of vaccine-type and immunity on the burden of COVID-19. *Math Biosci*. 2023;360.
 143. Sritipsukho P, Khawcharoenporn T, Siribumrungwong B, Damronglerd P, Suwantararat N, Satdhabudha A, et al. Comparing real-life effectiveness of various COVID-19 vaccine regimens during the delta variant-dominant pandemic: a test-negative case-control study. *Emerg Microbes Infections*. 2022;11(1):585–92.
 144. Braeye T, Catteau L, Brondeel R, van Loenhout JAF, Proesmans K, Cornelissen L, et al. Vaccine effectiveness against transmission of alpha, delta and omicron SARS-CoV-2-infection, Belgian contact tracing, 2021–2022. *Vaccine*. 2023;41(20):3292–300.
 145. Hsu L, Grüne B, Buess M, Joisten C, Klobucnik J, Nießen J et al. Covid-19 breakthrough infections and transmission risk: real-world data analyses from Germany's largest public health department (cologne). *Vaccines*. 2021;9(11).
 146. Althobaiti Y, Wu J, Tildesley MJ. Non-pharmaceutical interventions and their relevance in the COVID-19 vaccine rollout in Saudi Arabia and Arab Gulf countries. *Infect Disease Modelling*. 2022;7(3):545–60.
 147. Chhim S, Ku G, Mao S, Van De Put W, Van Damme W, Ir P et al. Descriptive assessment of COVID-19 responses and lessons learnt in Cambodia, January 2020 to June 2022. *BMJ Global Health*. 2023;8(5).
 148. Elhakim M, Tourab SB, Salem F, Van De Weerd R. Epidemiology of the first and second waves of COVID-19 pandemic in Djibouti and the vaccination strategy developed for the response. *BMJ Global Health*. 2022;7.
 149. Hong SA. Six pivotal lessons learned in South Korea for whole-of-Government Approach to successful COVID-19 vaccine rollout in Planetary Health. *OMICS J Integr Biology*. 2022;26(10):567–79.
 150. de Wolff T, Pflüger D, Rehme M, Heuer J, Bittner MI. Evaluation of pool-based testing approaches to enable population-wide screening for COVID-19. *PLoS ONE*. 2021;15(12 December).
 151. Sharma A, Oda G, Icardi M, Mole L, Holodny M. Implementation of large-scale laboratory-based detection of COVID-19 in the Veterans Health Administration, March 2020 – February 2021. *Diagn Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2022;102(3).
 152. Baik Y, Cilloni L, Kendall E, Dowdy D, Arinaminpathy N. Symptom-based vs asymptomatic testing for controlling SARS-CoV-2 transmission in low- and middle-income countries: a modelling analysis. *Epidemics*. 2022;41.
 153. Davis EL, Lucas TCD, Borlase A, Pollington TM, Abbott S, Ayabina D et al. Contact tracing is an imperfect tool for controlling COVID-19 transmission and relies on population adherence. *Nat Commun*. 2021;12(1).
 154. Kriegova E, Fillerova R, Raska M, Manakova J, Dihel M, Janca O et al. Excellent option for mass testing during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic: painless self-collection and direct RT-qPCR. *Virology*. 2021;18(1).
 155. Zirbes J, Sterr CM, Keller C, Engenhardt-Cabillic R, Nonnenmacher-Winter C, Günther F. Efficiency analysis of rapid antigen test based SARS-CoV-2 in hospital contact tracing and screening regime: test characteristics and cost effectiveness. *Diagn Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2023;106(4).
 156. Eyre DW, Futschik M, Tunkel S, Wei J, Cole-Hamilton J, Saquib R, et al. Performance of antigen lateral flow devices in the UK during the alpha, delta, and omicron waves of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic: a diagnostic and observational study. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*; 2023.
 157. Noreen N, Naveed I, Dil S, Niazi S, Saleem S, Mohiuddin N et al. Trend Analysis of exponential increase of Covid-19 cases in Pakistan: an interpretation. *Global Biosecur*. 2020;2(1).
 158. Webb E, Winkelmann J, Scarpetti G, Behmane D, Habicht T, Kahur K, et al. Lessons learned from the Baltic countries' response to the first wave of COVID-19. *Health Policy*. 2022;126(5):438–45.
 159. Alexander M, Unruh L, Koval A, Belanger W. United States response to the COVID-19 pandemic, January–November 2020. *Health Econ Policy Law*. 2022;17(1):62–75.
 160. Modisenyane M, Madikezela L, Mngemane S, Ramadan OP, Matlala M, McCarthy K, et al. COVID-19 response in South African communities: screening, testing, tracing and movement modelling. *South Afr Med J*. 2022;112(5b):366–70.
 161. Stanislawski N, Lange F, Fahnmann C, Riggers C, Wahalla MN, Porr M et al. Mobile SARS-CoV-2 screening facilities for rapid deployment and university-based diagnostic laboratory. *Eng Life Sci*. 2023;23(2).
 162. Cattaneo A, Vitali A, Mazzoleni M, Previdi F. An agent-based model to assess large-scale COVID-19 vaccination campaigns for the Italian territory: the case study of Lombardy region. Volume 224. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*; 2022.
 163. Rainisch G, Jeon S, Pappas D, Spencer KD, Fischer LS, Adhikari BB, et al. Estimated COVID-19 cases and hospitalizations averted by Case Investigation and contact tracing in the US. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2022;5(3):E224042.
 164. Bayram JD, Sauer LM, Catlett C, Levin S, Cole G, Kirsch TD et al. Critical resources for Hospital Surge Capacity: An Expert Consensus Panel. *PLoS Currents*. 2013(OCT).
 165. Fillat-Gomà F, Coderch-Navarro S, Martínez-Carreres L, Monill-Raya N, Nadal-Mir T, Lalmolda C, et al. Integrated 3D printing solution to mitigate shortages of airway consumables and personal protective equipment during the COVID-19 pandemic. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2020;20(1):1–8.
 166. Lansbury LE, Rodrigo C, Leonardi-Bee J, Nguyen-Van-Tam J, Lim WS. Corticosteroids as adjunctive therapy in the treatment of influenza: an updated Cochrane systematic review and meta-analysis. *Crit Care Med*. 2020;48(2):e98–106.
 167. Lehnert R, Pletz M, Reuss A, Schaberg T. Antiviral medications in seasonal and pandemic influenza: a systematic review. *Deutsches Ärzteblatt International*. 2016;113(47):799.
 168. Jones JC, Yen HL, Adams P, Armstrong K, Govorkova EA. Influenza antivirals and their role in pandemic preparedness. *Antiviral Res*. 2023;210.
 169. Yuan Y, Jiao B, Qu L, Yang D, Liu R. The development of COVID-19 treatment. *Front Immunol*. 2023;14:1125246.
 170. Cantini F, Goletti D, Petrone L, Najafi Fard S, Niccoli L, Foti R. Immune therapy, or antiviral therapy, or both for COVID-19: a systematic review. *Drugs*. 2020;80(18):1929–46.
 171. Li G, Hilgenfeld R, Whitley R, De Clercq E. Therapeutic strategies for COVID-19: progress and lessons learned. *Nat Rev Drug Discovery*. 2023;22(6):449–75.
 172. Spinardi J, Dantas AC, Carballo C, Thakkar K, Akoury NA, Kyaw MH, et al. Narrative review of the evolution of COVID-19 vaccination recommendations in countries in Latin America, Africa and the Middle East, and Asia. *Infect Dis Therapy*. 2023;12(5):1237–64.
 173. Maleki B, Hojati Z. A precise review on NAATs-based diagnostic assays for COVID-19: a motion in fast POC molecular tests. *Eur J Clin Invest*. 2022;52(11).
 174. Belete TM. The Immune Response, Safety, and efficacy of Emergency Use authorization-granted COVID-19 vaccines: a review. *Open Microbiol J*. 2022;16(1).
 175. Gong W, Parkkila S, Wu X, Aspatwar A. SARS-CoV-2 variants and COVID-19 vaccines: current challenges and future strategies. *International Reviews of Immunology*; 2022.
 176. Qin Z, Sun Y, Zhang J, Zhou L, Chen Y, Huang C. Lessons from SARS CoV-2 and its variants (review). *Mol Med Rep*. 2022;26(2).

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